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Local Islanders' Involvement Determines Event Success

The success or failure of an event often depends on planning and coordination, which directly affect attendees' experiences. Especially today, public reactions to events, positive or negative, are amplified by social media. Negative feedback can quickly and widely harm an event's reputation.

Cultural and religious events play a vital role in Filipino culture by showcasing heritage, stimulating the local economy, and attracting tourists. Effective event organization, especially when locals are involved, increases the event's authenticity and impact. However, the benefits of such events depend on careful planning that actively considers the needs and voices of the local community. Including locals not only prevents problems but also ensures both residents and visitors benefit, making public consultation essential to event success.

Traffic flow is one of the problems that could arise during the influx of tourists; taking a cab could be difficult, and there is a possibility of a fare and commodity price hike during the event. These are the only few aspects of the event that could affect the locals. Proper planning and mitigation could protect locals from exploitation and lessen the negative impact.

Communities would gladly contribute to the event's success if they were part of the people behind it. When they are included, suggestions are heard, and support is recognized. Locals would likely need time to participate and represent their culture. Community engagement means helping the local government plan and execute the activities it will organize. Partnership with business owners and academe; ensuring the event is culturally appropriate; volunteers providing additional human resources for the event can foster a sense of ownership; and community members leveraging local networks to increase attendance during the activities. Using local resources could reduce event costs and enhance the event's quality. In an event like the Higatangan Island festival, which happens annually in the municipality of Naval, from an observer's perspective, the locals are hands-on in conceptualizing the event; they even offer homestead accommodations on festival day to accommodate tourists, providing authentic Higatanganon hospitality and cuisine. Tourists could ride a banca, dive, and experience the genuine Higatangan adventures.

This kind of act helps the festival succeed and generate income for the community. Despite challenges during planning, local involvement, islanders' unity, and government support ensure the event runs smoothly. When locals participate and feel included, cooperation and unity emerge, making the event successful.